

Opportunities and Challenges in Higher Education for Rural Area

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Abstract:

Education is the play important role in growing socio – economic. Higher education generate empowerment in rural youth. Rual youth giving opportunities to develop himself, develop different type of skills, techniques. Higher education is power to transform rural youth in human capital. We think here only in rural area of state of the Maharashtra. State Maharashtra was given many educators, Philosopher's to nation. Maharashtra is progressive state in India. Higher education now rune New Education Policy (NEP 2020) in overall in Maharashtra state. Actually, working NEP 2020 in rural area. Now many rural areas education institutions and organisation give different opportunities and face challenges. Opportunities are students' available digital education, learn different skills, high quality education in accessible and affordable. But also face challenges is not available proper infrastructures, un skill and not qualified staff available, lack of knowledge of education in rural area etc. This research is study over all impact of higher education on rural area. Researcher find out some opportunities and challenges of higher education for rural area. This study aim is known and understand opportunities and challenges of higher education in rural area in Maharashtra.

Keywords: Higher Education, NEP 2020, Challenges, Opportunities, Development.

Introduction:

Education is the transmission of Skills and Knowledge and growth and development of human. Education is main factor effected to growing economic development of nation. Education divided in two types formal and informal. Formal education given in school, institute and colleges. Informal education from home, family, society etc. Education is a main pallor of development of nation. Formal education divide in different level Pre-primary, Primary, Secondary and Higher education. Formal education under the government guidelines. NEP 2020 is also formal education. This policy also run through guidelines of government.

Review of Literature:

The researcher uses the source for these research paper has been collected form the already published on these topics in online books, platform, website, periodicals government report etc.

Prashant Vijay sing Patil 2023 this article has find out the A framework that views students, parents, and communities as citizens with rights and the right to participate is necessary for the implement education.

Prof. Shamal S. Choudhary, DR. Archana Sanjay Desai August 2025 these research case study finds out the change the approach of education. Youth give the opportunities to get job and challenges in operating of NEP in rural area is big task.

Objective of the Study:

Main objective of this research is to study of knowing NEP 2020 and Opportunities and challenges of Higher education in rural area of Maharashtra. The aim of this study is to provide information in rural development with an overview of basic education in Higher education in rural areas, as well as what is being done to improve it and how they can help.

Following is main objective of this study.

1. To study the Education, Higher Education and NEP 2020 concept.
2. To study the challenges of higher education in rural area.
3. To study the opportunities of higher education in rural area.

Research Methodology:

This research basis on secondary data. This research is descriptive type. This research uses secondary data from various government websites, magazines, newspaper, research paper, journals, published data etc.

Study Area:

Higher education institutions and organisation in Maharashtra state. Maharashtra state is diverted in different district and villages. Geographically diversity in every rural area of Maharashtra state. Also, educationally development is not equally in all over Maharashtra.

Higher institutions in Maharashtra state are following

1. One Central University
2. Twenty-Three State University
3. Twenty-one Deemed Universities
4. IIT Bombay and TISS is premier institutes in Maharashtra state.

Higher education in rural are of Maharashtra expanded education, vocational and technical education through 23 universities and

colleges all over Maharashtra. The Maharashtra state run the programme of Unnat Maharashtra Abhiyan to connect rural colleges. NEP 2020 to give skill-based education, scholarship, digital education to different college students in all over state. Higher education Sico-economic development of Maharashtra through generating employment skill in college students.

Opportunities of Higher education in Rural Area:

Higher education gives the skill-based education and generate job for college students. Higher education MU with different Industries and institutions. We explain the opportunities of higher education in rural area through the following point from all over the study of this research topic.

1.Skill Based Education: Rural area basic problem of students has not skill related to job.

Higher education provides different skill course through higher education. Also develop local skill through education.

2. Community Engagement: Higher education run different course and syllabus related to special related subject. Student also know, study, research the local problem of society and give the solution to society.

3. Improve Research Approach: Higher education develop the research approach in students through the field project related to students' special subject. Student understanding research concept.

4. Digital Knowledge: Higher education NEP 2020 give students digital knowledge and provide technical Skill through Syllabus. Students are fulfilling the technical and digital requirement of industries.

5. Update Teacher: Not only update student also teacher update knowledge of technical, research, project and digital. Teacher uses various tools in teaching.

6. Innovating Teaching and Learning: Higher education students and teachers give opportunities to developed the teaching and learning skill. Use different innovating teaching process for students understand.

7. Financial helps: Higher education give different type of scholarship through government, Ngo. And others proved rural students, female students. Financial support to students for gives higher education.

8. Involvements of Society and stakeholder's: Higher education involve different type of stakeholder's parents, management, students, teachers, government, society, etc. So, everyone involves the process of developing in higher education.

9. Reduce Drop out: Higher education aim is reducing the drop out percentage in higher education. So, government give different type financial scholarship to students. Relaxation in fees etc.

Challenges of Higher Education in Rural Area:

Higher education working different colleges and institutions. Every institutions not same. We are always explain different in Bharat and India. This same condition in Rural and Urban area. Rural areas are some basic problem so they face the challenges running higher education NEP 2020 policy. Through the researcher understand the some challenges of higher education in rural area are explaining through the following point.

1. Awareness: Rural areas students and stakeholder's not aim objective of higher education. Higher education policy not implemented as proper of the lack of awareness.

2. Unskilled Staff: Most of college and institutions staff was not different digital, technical skills. So, staff cannot transform skill perfect to students.

3. Unaided Colleges: There are 2976 private unaided colleges in Maharashtra as per the data 2021. Unaided colleges have capital, infrastructure, qualified staff etc problem face. They cannot properly follow guidelines of government.

4. Lack of training to staff: Government implement policy first and then they conduct the workshop and training session. Not clarity in syllabus, Evaluation, workload etc. in staff and government agencies till date.

5. Lack of Infrastructure: In rural area not basic infrastructure, Light, water, transport etc. Higher education policy not working in properly.

6. High-Cost investment: Higher Education NEP 2020 require computer lab etc. This facility not provide every institute in rural area.

7. Management not understand: Higher education policies and guidelines not understand local rural management understand.

So, we cannot properly follow higher education in rural area.

Conclusion:

Higher education is important role play growing economic development in rural area. NEP 2020 higher education MU with different Industries and NGOs. Higher education develop skill in student and provide employment to students. Its impact on rural areas develop leveling standard of local people and improve the economic development. Higher education provide many opportunities for rural area developing in Maharashtra. Also Face some problem lack of infrastructure, unskilled staff, capital, language, awareness etc. Without education not develop rural area also state and nation. Higher education implemented many policy to improve the percentage of education rural area. And reduce the drop out percentage in higher education.

NEP 2020 is give new approach to education. Subject, Project etc. confuse to teacher

and students. Evaluation pattern of student is very difficult to students and teachers. Higher education develop research approach in students and teachers.

References:

1. Prashant Vijaysing Patil Revisiting the Rural Education and Their Attainment Towards Societal Development: A Comparative Study of Maharashtra State. Jayasinghe et al. (Eds.): ICETBM 2023, AEBMR 242, pp. 304–308, 2023. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-94-6463-162-3_27
2. Prof. Shamal S. Choudhary, DR. Archana Sanjay Desai Online & Print International, Peer Reviewed, Refereed & Indexed Monthly Journal www.rajimr.com
3. Baloj, D., Shantinath A. (2021a). Status of Higher Education in Rural Areas of India. International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT), 9(8), e497–e504. https://doi.org/https://ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT_2108509.pdf
4. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Education>
5. <https://educationforallinindia.com/improving-education-in-rural-india>